

IMPACT OF HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES ON EMPLOYEE TURNOVER INTENTION

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Received Date: 19/08/2021

Accepted Date: 19/10/2021

Published Date: 20/11/2021

ABSTRACT

Recently, the academic and non-academic staff turnover rate at a local university in Selangor, Malaysia, has increased, and the cause for resignation is unclear. This study investigates the employee perception of human resource management practices and their turnover intention. A thorough literature review suggests that performance appraisal, working conditions, equal employment opportunity, training & development, and rewards are the turnover determinants in the Malaysian context. This study considered the equity theory of motivation model, known as Adam's equity theory of motivation. The primary data was collected through a survey questionnaire involving 140 academic and non-academic staff. The 5-point Likert scale was used in constructing the items of the survey questionnaire. The majority of the respondents are females between the age of 26 and 35. They are Malays married, have an educational qualification of a bachelor's degree, earn between the range of RM 3,500 and RM4,000, and work as lecturers and executives. The Cronbach's Alpha for turnover intention, performance appraisal, working conditions, training and development, and rewards is 0.600, 0.677, 0.774, 0.805, 0.680, and 0.772. Pearson correlation shows that turnover intention is significantly negatively correlated with performance appraisal ($r=-0.632$), working condition ($r=-0.404$), equal employment opportunity ($r=-0.454$), training & development ($r=-0.189$), and rewards ($r=-0.102$). The multiple regression model's R-square value is 35.8%. The hypotheses test results reveal a significant relationship between all the independent and dependent variables. This study supported the motivation theory model where better performance appraisal, working conditions, training and development opportunities, and a better reward system is important to reduce employees' intention to turnover.

Keywords: human resource management practices, employee turnover intention, education, motivation, university

INTRODUCTION

Over the years, employee turnover has been a challenging problem for all businesses and organizations. In the most recent business environment, which is highly competitive, human capital is a fundamental part whereby employers have to take good care of their employees. In the past few years, the turnover rate of employees has increased in various sectors. It was estimated that each time a corporation or organization replaces an employee, the average cost is six to nine

months' salary. For example, a manager who draws a salary of \$40,000 annually will incur the cost for the organization approximately \$ 20,000 to \$30,000 just in hiring and training costs (Kurniawaty et al., 2019). A high personnel turnover rate will delay project completion and reduces overall project productivity. When a person with knowledge and experience in a certain role leaves, the scheduling activities will be delayed since replacing someone well-versed with the designated tasks is time-consuming. Hiring new employees will incur more costs and resources to learn, follow the procedures, and adjust to the new working environment.

Human resources (HR) is an important resource in any organization. In order to achieve the organization's goals and objectives, adequate management of HR plays a vital role in any organization. A human Resource Management practice impacts employees' collaboration and interpersonal trust to exploit employees' awareness of turnover intention. Research shows that emotional participation is directly and positively affected by training, development, and reward systems (Ju and Li, 2019). Ahmad (2018) reported that better evaluation of job content and job context by the employees leads to a sense of obligation and commitment toward the organization, hence reducing their intentions to discord organizational membership. In recent years, the turnover rate in an organization has been increasing in Malaysia. Employees' desire to walk away from any organization can be seen as an endeavour by employees to migrate towards a different organization that meets their unique needs. The high incidence of employee turnover in today's environment motivates organizations and businesses to improve their staff retention tactics.

According to Harvard Business Review (2020), the education industry functions as a back bone to a nation since it produces the "future of a nation". Human capital at the university is critical to its entire operation and the achievement of its strategic goals. Healthier employee retention of an institution impacts positively towards the institute's operations. Academic staff does not only perform teaching and conduct a research activity which intends to solve future predicted or ongoing issues. Employee turnover in education institutions negatively impacts the teaching environment and reduces the number of researchers. University's global ranking also depends on the number of research conducted. In the meantime, non-academic employee turnover impacts the institution's daily operations (Times Higher Education World University Ranking, 2020; Elsevier, 2020).

In Malaysia, the worker turnover rate expanded from 1.1percent to 13.2 percent in 2014 and expanded to 14.3 percent in 2017, and fabricating business bunch experienced a high staff turnover (Ju and Li, 2019).

Table 1: Malaysian Education Institution Turnover Illustration

Measuring Organization	Acceptable Turnover Rate	Malaysian Institution Turnover Rate
LinkedIn Corporation (LinkedIn, 2018)	$\leq 10.9\%$	
U.S. Bureau of Statistics (TalentLyft, 2018)	$\leq 12\%$	18%
Glassdoor (Chamberlain, 2017)	$\leq 10\%$	(Ramasamy & Abdullah, 2017)
Monster (Peoplehr, 2017)	$\leq 15\%$	

Table 1 illustrates the employee turnover condition among Malaysian education institutions. Several Human Resources online specialists and consultancies such as LinkedIn Corporation, Glassdoor and Monster report a healthier turnover rate of 10.9 percent or below, 10 percent or below and 15 percent or below. However, the current Malaysian education institution's employee turnover rate shows abnormal rate, which is 18 percent (Ramasamy & Abdullah, 2017). Education News agencies reported that roughly 51.7 percent of academic staff work at universities and colleges and intend to find new jobs rather than stay at the same institution.

The above-mentioned Human Resource specialist bodies also measure a healthier retention rate as 90 percent or above and 85 percent or above. However, the current trend of Malaysian education institutions shows a retention rate of 82 percent only, which is much lower than the default healthier rate. As mentioned in the Borneo Post Seeds, the principal subject that has gathered attention and is indispensable among Malaysian education institutions is mainly voluntary turnover (Borneo Post Seeds, 2017). This voluntary turnover rate significantly created an unclear path in career stability and an imbalanced situation in the faculty operations of universities. According to Ramasamy and Abdullah (2017), this present issue faced by education institutions needs investigation as the number of education institutions establishments increases yearly. Moreover, this turnover issue negatively has impacted the sustainability of the global education ranking.

Qualified and good academicians are the most important assets for the university to generate competent and universal graduates. The academic institutions' HR incurs a high cost for recruitment purposes. Thus, Human Resource Management practices are crucial in an organization as quality HR practices can push up employees' affective commitment toward their companies. Employee turnover has become an unavoidable issue to be investigated to find proper and effective strategies for employee retention.

There is a need to investigate the determinants of employee turnover intention in educational institutions. This study investigates employee turnover intention in a university and the influence of five Human Resource Management factors (Performance appraisal, working conditions, equal employment opportunity, training & development, and rewards).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Based on Sinniah & Kamil (2017), the efforts that the managers take in performance management intervention significantly improve the outcome, which is the employee turnover intention by decreasing the intention and increasing employee retention. This journal article aims to examine how high-performance HR practices, which are the input action of an organization, affect the outcome of the performed action, which is the employee turnover intention. Another study by Sinniah et al. (2018) supports the selected variables, which are considered the input actions by Human Resource Management in educational institutions on motivating the employees to sustain in the job. As mentioned above, the sample was collected from 200 respondents in the study. The data analyzed through structural equation modelling indicates a negative association between HR practices and worker intention to turnover. The model further explains that high-performance HR practices may significantly increase employee sustainability and working conditions, which will change employee turnover intention. This study also recommends that educational institutions develop HR systems to help the management attract and retain the talented workforce.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The conceptual framework is shown in Figure 1. The dependent variable is Employees Turnover Intention, and there are five independent variables Performance appraisal, working conditions, equal employment opportunity, training & development, and rewards.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL AND EMPLOYEE TURNOVER INTENTION

Sinnaiah and Kamil (2017) stated that a clearly articulated human resource management practice in every company's constitution significantly reduces employee turnover intention. Performance appraisal regarding career development significantly motivates employees to sustain themselves on the job and decreases the intention to leave the workplace (Chin, 2018). Similarly, Davidescu (2020) found a negative association between job satisfaction and employee turnover intention. Therefore, the first hypothesis H1: There is a significant relationship between performance appraisal and employee turnover intention in University XYZ, is proposed.

WORKING CONDITIONS AND EMPLOYEE TURNOVER INTENTION

Sinnappan (2017) explains that the employee turnover intention is inter-related to their performance, which is positively influenced by the working condition where they are working. In the same study, restructuring was also mentioned under working conditions, and respondents revealed that restructuring processes only increase the workload rather than improving skills. There are higher chances; that the employee decides to leave the job as soon as the restructuring process occurs. The employees' productivity significantly decreases if working conditions such as bullying exist in the workplace (Paul and Kee, 2020). When employees work according to their desired hours, they tend to be more motivated and spend more time in the same job. Employee's health condition significantly moderates or mediates the association between the working condition and job satisfaction (Hafeez et al., 2019). On the other hand, Hafeez et al. (2019) reported that the association between working condition and job satisfaction may change if any moderation is involved. Therefore, H2: There is a significant relationship between working conditions and employees' turnover intention in University XYZ is proposed.

EQUAL EMPLOYMENT OPPORTUNITY AND EMPLOYEE TURNOVER INTENTION

Most discussed topics in the database justify that female employee usually gets only lower positions than male employee, and they do not get equal opportunities in career development (Wikaningrum and Yuniawan, 2018). Widayati, Widjaya and Lia (2019) critically argued that when there is a higher level of gender discrimination that leads to unequal employment opportunities, employees leave the premises. It is very difficult to determine the exact issue of the cause of unequal employment opportunity in terms of gender, though government regulations around the globe strictly implement equal employment to influence the labour market flow (Leibbrandt and List, 2018). However, Alonso, Moscoso and Salgado (2017) reported that indirect discrimination against women exists in some parts of the United States. They also investigated whether women are intentionally biased during the interview or selection process. It was found that Structural Behavioural Interviews (SBI) are the most practised strategy that discourages gender discrimination and leads to employment equality. Therefore, H3: There is a significant relationship between equal employment opportunity and employees' turnover intention in University XYZ is proposed.

TRAINING & DEVELOPMENT AND EMPLOYEE TURNOVER INTENTION

Widayati, Widjaya and Lia (2019) found that a better and well-designed human resource management practice significantly encourages the department to conduct training for the right people, leading to better employee performance. The employee turnover intention significantly shrunk when employees are fully occupied with better productivity. Moreover, besides rewarding, training sessions provided to employees significantly encourage the employees to sustain in the same job (Mendis, 2017). The employee's opinion of his or her boss was negatively connected to the likelihood of leaving (Malek, Kline and DiPietro, 2018). Furthermore, management training and management style were found to have a substantial inverse association with employee turnover intentions. Finally, according to this study, when manager training grows, employee turnover intentions drop. According to this study also, hotels that invest in management training have a lower likelihood of staff turnover. According to this study, workers could see the executives more favourably, sense nearer to the supervisors, and lower their wish to quit the firm if managers received more training. Furthermore, Ju and Li (2019) emphasize that job training is necessary for parties, management and employees and that this leads to a positive outcome based on their

empirical findings. Therefore, H4: There is a significant relationship between training & development and employee turnover intention in University XYZ.

REWARD AND EMPLOYEES' TURNOVER INTENTION

Widayati, Widjaya and Lia (2019) recommended that employers engage in offering a reward, which was empirically tested and confirmed that reward motivates employee satisfaction and the intention to leave the job decreases. Mendis (2017) found that the influence of the reward system is a very powerful predictor of labour turnover in Sri Lanka. The research provided evidence of a strong impact on employee turnover intention when there are better financial and non-financial rewards. It has been suggested that offering rewards may encourage the employees to think that the workplace management recognizes their value. This directly brings them hope and ensures their safety and workplace. Similarly, Kurniawaty, Ramlyb and Ramlawati (2019) reported that rewarding significantly increases employees' job satisfaction. A reward system that recognizes the employees significantly reduces turnover intention. However, the study from Aaron (2021) reveals that healthcare officers are willing to sustain themselves in the job when the management recognizes their empowerment in the name of reward. In addition, the research results show that structural authorization has an indirect negative impact on the intention of job rotation. Therefore, recognition of the empowerment of the individual is rewarding and significantly improves job satisfaction and reduces the turnover intention among employees. Therefore, H5: There is a significant relationship between reward and employees' turnover intention in University XYZ is proposed.

METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH DESIGN

A research design is a systematic direction which guides the researcher to proceed with the methodology (Sekaran 2020). It is the general strategy in which the investigators want to execute their research. This research design ensures proper data collection procedures to achieve the research objectives. The research method refers to how, where, when, and by what practical methods he or she wishes to collect and evaluate data. The study utilized a cross-sectional study design where data is collected through a survey via email to the target group of the study.

SAMPLING DESIGN

This study aims to investigate the factors that influence employee (academician and non-academician) turnover intentions at a local university in Selangor, Malaysia. The phrase "population" refers to the entire group of people, events, or items of interest in a study. The target population can be described as a specific group of people from whom researchers want to collect data or statistics (Chiat & Panatik, 2019). The target group for this study is the tutors, lecturers, assistant professors, associate professors, professors, and all other operations staff. A total of 200 questionnaires were distributed via online survey since a higher sample size will be an advantage to derive more accurate findings. The sampling frame was obtained from the university's HR department. The respondents were selected using a simple random sampling technique. The population size as of the 19th of February 2021 is 220, and this study targets a

sample of 140 respondents-based on the sample size table by Sekaran (2020). The questionnaires were emailed to the respondents.

Before performing the formal survey, it is necessary to confirm the validity of the questionnaires and make necessary modifications. For pilot testing, ten sets of pre-test samples were analyzed prior to the start of any formal survey. A total of 140 questionnaires were generated and delivered by email randomly via Google E-form. The survey was conducted from June 20th to June 28th, 2021.

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

In construct measurement, Likert scales are frequently used for data gathering in quantitative or mixed-method methods using survey instruments (Pescaroli et al. (2020). The questionnaire has two sections; Section A: Demographic Information and Section B: Likert scale items for measuring turnover intention, working conditions, equal employment opportunity, performance appraisal, training and development, and rewards. Each variable has 5 items. There are five scale options offered: 1=Completely disagree, 2=Somewhat Disagree, 3=Neither agree nor disagree, 4=Somewhat Agree and 5=Completely Agree. The items for each variable were selected and adopted based on past literature reviews in Kurniawaty, Ramlyb and Ramlawati (2019), Malek, Kline and DiPietro (2018), Ramasamy and Abdullah (2017) and Widayati, Widjaya and Lia (2019)

DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS

The descriptive analysis involved summary statistics such as mean, median, mode, variance, range, and standard deviation for continuous variables and frequency and percentage for categorical variables. The mode for the demographic variables such as gender, age, education qualification, religion, ethnicity, and respondent's position helped researchers draw a demographic profile of the respondents. The shape of the distribution of variables may be described through indices known as skewness and kurtosis. The usage of skewness and kurtosis is a part of normality analysis, which confirms whether the sample is normally distributed or not. The criteria of normality for the skewness and kurtosis are values in the range of -1 to +1 and -3 to +3 respectively.

RELIABILITY TEST

The reliability metric is Cronbach's alpha (Chan & Idris, 2017). Cronbach's alpha is calculated using the average correlation between items used to measure the construct. Generally, a Cronbach's alpha of 0.7 and above indicates internal consistency or construct reliability. Cronbach alpha is a scale that ranges from 0 (no consistency) to 1 (perfect consistency) (complete consistency). Cronbach's α will be defined as follows: $\alpha = 0.80$ to 0.95 (very reliable). $\alpha = 0.70$ to 0.80 (high level of reliability). $\alpha = 0.60$ to 0.70 , (reliable). $\alpha < 0.60$ (unreliable).

INFERENCE ANALYSIS

Inferential statistics are a type of statistic that aids in establishing associations between variables and drawing inferences from them. The hypothetical deductive technique necessitates the falsifiability of hypotheses. Null hypotheses are produced as a result. Propose null hypothesis (H_0) to reject the establishment of alternative hypothesis H_1 . It is considered correct until statistical evidence in the form of hypothesis testing proves otherwise. Inferential statistics provide the most important statistical evidence. SPSS is a data management and analysis program that can perform descriptive statistics such as charts, frequencies, charts, and lists and advanced

multivariate and inferential statistical programs such as analysis of variance (ANOVA), factor analysis, cluster analysis, and categorized data analysis.

PEARSON CORRELATION

The coefficient of Pearson correlation reveals the strength, focus, intensity, and significance of the link between all variables calculated at the interval or ratio level, according to Sekaran (2020). It was a statistical test of two variables interacting. For interval and ratio scaled variables, the Pearson correlation coefficient is acceptable. The coefficient of correlation (r) ranges from -1.0 to +1.0. A perfect negative linear association is shown by a value of r of -1.0, whereas r of +1.0 indicates a perfect positive linear association. When the r -value is 0, it means there is no association between the variables. The fact that one variable is a mirror image of the other is significant. We measure two variables, X and Y , for example. The greater the value recorded by variable X , the lower the value measured by variable Y , implying a proportional association where one increases while the other decreases. The correlation coefficient revealed the size and the direction of the linear association. Their covariance will be negative if the related values of X and Y diverge from their means in the opposite direction and vice versa.

MULTIPLE REGRESSION ANALYSIS

According to Baños et al. (2019), an estimation of a relationship study in which the effects of two or more independent variables on a single, interval-size dependent variable are assessed simultaneously is known as multiple regression analysis. The principles of multiple regression analysis are the same as those of basic regression analysis. In this case, researchers only use more than one independent variable to explain the variance of the dependent variable. Multiple regression analysis, a multivariate method, is commonly used in business research. Multiple regression analysis, of course, begins with the conceptual model (and the hypotheses derived from it) that the researcher developed earlier in the research process. When there are several independent variables, researchers utilize multiple regressions to describe the variation of the dependent variable. Standardized regression coefficients are the results of a multiple regression analysis performed on variables that have been standardized (or beta coefficients). It is an extension of simple regression analysis that permits numerous independent factors to predict the predictability of a single dependent variable. For example, one independent variable, performance appraisal, can explain turnover intention (dependent variable). This is typically done to allow the researcher to examine the relative effects of independent factors on the dependent variable when the independent variables are measured in various units of measurement. This study allowed for evaluating two or more independent variables simultaneously as one dependent variable. As a result, instead of just one predictor variable, several regression equations represented the values of many variables.

In general, multiple regression models could be expressed as below:

$$Y = a + b_1 \cdot X_1 + b_2 \cdot X_2 + \dots + b_p \cdot X_p + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

Where

Y = Dependent variable a = constant

b_p = the regression coefficient associated with the independent variables, X

X_p = the independent variables, where $p = 1, 2, 3, \dots$

ε = an error term, normally distributed about a mean of 0 (for computation, the ε is assumed to be 0).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RESPONDENTS' DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE

A total of 200 questionnaires were distributed via an online survey to university staff; only 140 respondents completed and returned the questionnaire. Female respondents outnumbered male respondents by a factor of two. The sample comprised 91 female (65%) and 49 male (35 %) respondents. The respondents' ages were divided into five categories: under 26, 26-35, 36-45, 46-55, and beyond 55. The majority (70%) of the respondents were between 26 and 35 years old. Malays were the major group of respondents (67%), followed by Chinese participants (20%). The majority (82%) were married (114 persons), followed by 15.7 percent (22 respondents) who were single, and the remaining 2.3 percent (4 respondents) were Divorced/Separated). About 43.6 percent (61 respondents) have a Bachelor's degree, followed by a PhD (28%), Diploma(15%), Masters(12.4%) and professional qualification (1%). About 76.4% of respondents' salaries were in the range of RM3501-RM4500. Next is dominated by the salary range of above RM2501-RM3500, with 13.6 percent representing 19 respondents. This is followed by RM5501-RM6500 with 5.8 percent and RM1501-RM2500 with 2.8 percent with 8 and 4 respondents each respectively. The least category is from respondents with a salary range above RM6500, with only 1.4 percent representing 2 respondents. The majority of the participants were others, whereby 70% representing 21 respondents and 20% represented 6 administrative staff respondents. The next job title holding it is Associate Professor, Senior Lecturers being at 3 percent and Tutors with 4 percent, each representing 1 respondent accordingly.

RELIABILITY ANALYSIS

The Cronbach's alpha for reward (0.774), Working Condition (0.805) and Training and Development (0.772) are greater than 0,7, indicating high internal consistency of reliability. Meanwhile, Cronbach's alpha for Performance Appraisal (0.677), Equal Employment Opportunity (0.680) and Turnover Intention (0.600) is in the range of 0.6-0.7, and thus the items can be considered reliable.

Table 2: The Cronbach's Alpha for all variables

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Results of Reliability	Number of Items, n
Turnover Intention	0.600	Good	5
Performance Appraisal	0.677	Good	5
Reward	0.774	Very Good	5
Working Condition	0.805	Very Good	5
Equal Employment Opportunity	0.680	Good	5
Training & Development	0.772	Very Good	5

NORMALITY ANALYSIS
Table 3: Normality analysis

	Valid	Skewness	Kurtosis
Turnover Intention	140	0.295	-1.922
Performance Appraisal	140	0.385	-1.860
Working Condition	140	0.149	-1.987
Equal Employment Opportunity	140	0.285	-1.928
Rewards	140	0.236	-1.953
Training & Development	140	0.246	-1.949

The table above shows the normality test outcome. All the variables are normally distributed since the Skewness and Kurtosis are in the range of -1 to +1 and -3 to +3 respectively

CORRELATION ANALYSIS

Table 4: Pearson Correlation

	Turnover Intention	Performance Appraisal	Reward	Working Condition	EEQ	Training & development
Turnover Intention	1	-0.632*	-0.102*	-0.404*	-0.454*	-0.189*
Performance Appraisal	-0.632*	1	0.352*	0.302*	0.213	0.664*
Reward	-0.102*	0.352*	1	0.676*	0.254*	0.109
Working condition	-0.404*	0.302*	0.676*	1	0.583*	0.576*
EEQ	-0.454*	0.213	0.254*	0.583	1	0.127
Training & development	-0.189*	0.664*	0.109	0.576*	0.127	1

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

According to the Pearson test, there is a significant negative association ($p < 0.05$) between the performance system and turnover intention, as shown by the Pearson Correlation Test. The performance system has a -0.632 association with the likelihood of turnover. This demonstrates that when performance appraisals are better, turnover intention rates get reduced. Furthermore, the negative association could be viewed as improved performance appraisal, which lessens the likelihood of job turnover. Performance appraisal also has a significant positive association between rewards in working conditions, equal employment opportunity, and training and development as 0.352, 0.302, 0.213, and 0.664 respectively. A slightly high correlation could be noticeable between training and development and performance appraisal. It could be interpreted that once an employee is offered training and development, the performance appraisal will favour the employee.

Due to the negative value of the correlation coefficient being -0.102, the Pearson correlation test in Table 4 indicates a significant negative association ($p < 0.05$) between reward and turnover intention. The reward variable has a -0.102 correlation with turnover intention, suggesting that while the reward is large, the turnover intention is low. The two variables have a reversible link. This also suggests that there is a negative association between reward and the likelihood of turnover. As a result, there is a weak and negative link between reward and the likelihood of turnover. The p-value for reward and turnover is smaller than the alpha value of 0.05, indicating a significant link between reward and turnover intention. When the other variables are taken into consideration, the reward also has a positive and significant correlation between working conditions, equal employment opportunity, and training and development. The highest correlation between rewards and working conditions can be seen (0.676, $p < 0.05$). When an employee is rewarded, this scenario could create better working conditions in the workplace. Due to the correlation coefficient value -0.404, there is a significant negative association ($p < 0.05$) between working conditions and turnover intention. This demonstrates that when working conditions are good, the turnover intention is low. The two variables have a reversible link. This indicates a weak and unfavourable association between working conditions and turnover intention. The p-value of 0.025 is lower than the alpha value of 0.05. Additionally, the working condition positively correlates with performance appraisal, equal employment opportunity, and training and development at 0.302, 0.583, and 0.576. The highest correlation can be seen between equal employment opportunity, and working condition means the working condition get better when employees experience equal opportunity.

Because the correlation coefficient value is -0.454, according to the Pearson correlation test shown in Table 4, there is a significant negative association ($p < 0.05$) between equal employment opportunity and turnover intention. This demonstrates that when equitable employment opportunity is great, employee turnover is low, owing to reasonable job satisfaction. This demonstrates a negative association between equal employment opportunities and turnover intention. The p-value is smaller than the alpha value of 0.05, indicating that equal employment opportunity and turnover intentions have a significant negative relationship. Equal employment opportunity also has a positive correlation between other variables, as mentioned above, and the highest correlation could be seen between working conditions. According to the Pearson correlation test, there is a significant negative correlation ($p < 0.05$) between training and development and employee turnover intention. This is because the correlation coefficient is negative. This demonstrates that when training & development levels are high, the likelihood of turnover is low. The value of the correlation coefficient is -0.189. This suggests a weak and negative link between training & development and turnover intention. Because the p-value is less than the alpha value of 0.05, there is a significant link between training & development and turnover intentions.

MULTIPLE REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Table 5: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	Std. The error in the Estimate
1	.598 ^a	0.358	0.224	0.63176

Table 6: ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean	F	Sig.
Regression	244.489	5	16.905	52.769	0.000***
Residual	189.923	607	0.313		
Total	194.779	608	0.32		

Table 7: Multiple Regression Analysis

Model	Unstandardized Beta		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	2.548	0.862		2.956	0.007
Performance Appraisal	-0.508	0.416	-0.412	1.221	0.034
Reward	-0.361	0.252	-0.348	-1.431	0.045
Working Condition	-0.039	0.221	-0.038	-1.74	0.033
Equal Employment	-0.496	0.226	-0.432	2.193	0.038
Training & Development	-0.443	0.24	-0.381	-1.848	0.027

According to the model explanation above, the R square value is 0.358, or 35.8%. This means that the five independent variables can explain 35.8% of the dependent variable of turnover intention. The independent variables are the performance appraisal, reward, working conditions, equal opportunity employment, and training & development; explain this research in a 35.8 per cent as the determinants for the turnover intention. The rest 64.2 percent of the factors are not covered in this study. Further, refer to Table 6, the F-value in the ANOVA shows 52.769 and a significant outcome. Based on Table 7, the multiple regression equation is formed. Turnover intention = 2.548 - 0.508(performance appraisal) - 0.361(reward) - 0.039 (working condition) -0.496 (equal employment opportunity) - 0.443 (training). This suggests that a one-unit increase in the performance appraisal system may result in a 0.508-unit drop in turnover intention, and this impact of significance with a p-value of 0.034 ($p < 0.05$).

On the other hand, every rise of 1 unit in the independent variable of reward causes a drop of 0.361 units in the dependent variable, the turnover intention with a significant impact ($P=0.045$, $P<0.05$). The rise in value decrease of 0.039 units in turnover intention can be caused by one working condition unit. This effect is also significant at 5 percent since the $P=0.033$ ($P<0.05$). Increases in equal employment opportunities may result in a decrease in the turnover intention of 0.496 units ($P<0.038$). The final independent variable, training that increases by 1 unit, results in a 0.443 reduction in turnover intention significantly since $P<0.05$).

H1: There is a significant association between performance appraisal and turnover intention, which is supported. Results showed a negative relationship between performance appraisal and employee turnover intention. This result aligns with the study of simultaneously Nutakor (2019) and Nawaz et al. (2019).

H2: There is a significant relationship between reward and turnover intention, which is supported. The results showed a significant negative relationship between employee turnover intention and their rewards. Ahmed and Sadia (2017) led an investigation in banks in Pakistan to know the impact of remunerations on employee performance. The organization utilizes the performance evaluation program for pay and advancement to give the employees. It has been inspected that the organization regularly plays the political game on it. The management and head of the association tend to apprise better those employees who have a great connection with a boss and back his positive or negative choice. Mendis (2017) reported a significant negative association between awards and the intention of employees to leave the logistics industry in Sri Lanka. He also suggested that the reward system of organizations needs to be improvised economically and non-economically since there is a strong negative association between the reward system and turnover intention. If the reward system seems successful and pleasing to workers, their turnover intention will be lowered steadily.

H3: There is a significant association between working conditions and turnover intention, which is supported. There is a strong link between working conditions and the possibility of turnover perceived working conditions, according to Ju and Li (2019), relate to a variety of negative employee actions, including plans to leave. Both perceived working conditions and turnover intentions are negatively related to the purpose of work. According to mediation analyses, several poor working conditions had indirect consequences on turnover intentions for the meaning of work. As a result, rising levels of unfavourable working conditions will increase turnover intentions.

H4: There is a significant relationship between equal employment opportunity and turnover intention, which is supported. In this study, the relationship between equal job opportunity and turnover intention is considerable. The findings suggest that equitable work opportunities have an impact on turnover intentions. When fair employment opportunity is great, the likelihood of turnover is low. It is helpful for an institute to ensure equal employment opportunities to reduce employee turnover. Based on Lee et al. (2019)'s quantitative data acquired from their survey, it was discovered that a lack of career growth chance is also significantly related to a higher turnover intention and a lower level of organizational commitment partially mediates it. Furthermore, it is proven in our study that the employees pay more attention to equal employment opportunity than performance appraisal, reward, working conditions and training. An individual's decision to leave an organization may be influenced by the lack of fair work opportunities in the organization. As a result, the link between equitable job possibilities and the likelihood of turnover was established.

H5: There is a significant relationship between training & development and turnover intention. This hypothesis is supported as results show a significant negative relationship between training and development and employee turnover. This study result aligns with the study of simultaneously Widayati, Widjaya & Lia (2019) and Malek, Kline & DiPietro (2018).

However, the study on private universities in Pakistan by Ishtiaq Ahmed (2018) reported that training & development did not significantly influence turnover intention, while Juhazi et al. (2018) reported a significant negative influence on turnover intentions. There is a considerable link between training and turnover intention. The training programs would increase employee happiness, promote morale, improve each employee's competency, and influence employee turnover intentions.

CONCLUSION

This study investigated the human resource practices' impact on employee turnover intention at a local university in Malaysia. Human resource practices such as performance appraisals, working conditions, equal employment opportunities, training & development, and rewards significantly affect employee turnover. This study is vital for institutions of higher learning as it confirms the importance of Human Resource Management and employee turnover intention. Employees are more inclined to leave if they are unsure about their performance appraisal, reward procedure, poor working conditions, lack of training, or unequal job opportunities. This research could be extended to other sectors such as the food, manufacturing, and hospitality sectors.

LIMITATIONS

FUTURE RESEARCH RECOMMENDATIONS

The R2 of our study is 0.358. As a result, 5 independent variables account for 35.8 percent of the variation in turnover intention. However, 5 of the independent variables in our study failed to clarify 64.2 percent of the variance in turnover intention. This suggests that other independent variables may influence turnover intention variation. Potentially, research on this proposition can be done towards the different populations covering public and private institutions. Hence, in the future, it would be more interesting to expand the sample to employees from different geographical locations, both inside and outside of UNITAR. Correspondingly, similar studies can be done at different levels, such as the maintenance department, administrative department, and record management departments, to get a holistic respondent view of HRM practices in relation to the turnover rate. Furthermore, a clear procedure should be maintained to collect online survey data. Therefore, it may confirm the data responses, in a repeated invitation should be sent to samples in a reasonable time frame, mentioning to take part whoever has never participated.

Most imperatively, a large sample size is more representative of the population, reducing the influence of exceptions or extreme observations. A sufficiently bigger sample size is also vital to produce results among essentially different variables. Additionally, having a mixed-method approach such as interviews as a data collection method can help resolve most of the shortcomings of data collection techniques by allowing the interviewer to develop a deeper understanding of the thinking behind the respondents' answers and learn information that they may have missed otherwise. Besides that, focus group discussions take the collaborative advantages of an interview to the next level by bringing together a carefully selected group for a moderated discussion on the survey's subject. It allows researchers to see both sides of the

argument, establish a balanced opinion on the subject, and discover details that they might not have expected.

It is also recommended to choose the longitude method when testing employee turnover intention variables. For example, post-test and pre-test choices would be the best method to test how each of the variables impacts employees' turnover intention. Researchers should choose a group of employees as a control group. In the meantime, they could also choose another group as a test group. The test and control groups should be tested on how a variable, such as training & development, impacts. After that, the test group should be given an actual training session. Upon completion of the training & development, both groups, testing and control groups, should be tested on their turnover intention. If the testing group show a significant improvement in their turnover intention, it could help the researchers to conclude with strong empirical evidence. Moreover, human behaviour gets modified due to external factors. This study collected data during the Covid-19 Pandemic situation. The respondents of this study might have reflected a mixed opinion regarding their turnover intention. It is suggested that future researchers focus on how employees' turnover intention is during and after the Covid-19 Pandemic situation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors thank UNITAR International University for the support of the publication of this research.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest regarding this manuscript.

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR

All authors are participants in the data collection and analysis and writing and revising the manuscript.

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